

Analysis of Recruitment Strategies in Efforts to Improve Employee Performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine and analyze the effect of the recruitment strategies (recruitment process and selection procedures) in efforts to improve employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea both partially and simultaneously. Furthermore, formulating appropriate policies and strategies to be implemented to improve the company. This research is categorized as quantitative research with associative methods and using questionnaires as research instruments. The population in this study are new employees of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea in the last 3 years. The sampling technique used the slovin formula with a purposive sampling technique with a total sample of 84 people. The method used for hypothesis testing in this study is the method of multiple linear regression. Based on the research that has been done, it is obtained that the recruitment process and selection procedure simultaneously had a positive and significant effect on employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. The recruitment process partially had a positive but not significant effect on employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. Partial selection procedure had a positive and significant effect on employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. Partially the selection procedure is the most dominant variable affecting the employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea.

Keywords: Recruitment Strategies, Recruitment Process, Selection Procedures, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Changes that are increasingly fast and can not be predicted to make competition in the global business world, demanding corporate management must be more concerned in managing human resources to be more productive. The company does not only need human resources that only fulfill the needs, but also human resources who do have sufficient competence and high commitment. The process of human resource management in general includes recruitment and selection, training and development, remuneration, termination, and also various employee behaviors that can have an impact on the running of work processes (Landy and Conte, 2013).

Good employee management starts with the management of a good recruitment process. Recruitment is the vanguard of the process of managing human resources. The decision to recruit new employees is an important decision for any company. The company must be able to recruit candidates who are not only suitable for the work in question but also the employee must be in line with company culture. Currently recruiting the best candidates that fit the company's needs has become a challenge. The company must be able to attract the attention of a number of potential people to fill vacant positions that need to be filled immediately by the right employees. To facilitate the process of recruiting

prospective workers, the company must have a large collection of candidate data. When the company has a store of data that contains a large selection of prospective candidates, the recruiter will easily select the candidate from the data set. Ideally, a recruitment process is aimed at gathering data sets about candidates who are considered prospective for further selection, so that the company represented by the recruiter can easily select the candidates at any time as needed. The various tools and methods used in recruitment must be adjusted to the characteristics of the prospective candidates being targeted so that they are interested in reading the job advertisements that have been made. Furthermore, of course it is expected that candidates wish to apply for positions that are needed.

The process of recruitment of human resources is very important to note, this is due to ensure that there is no discrepancy between what the company wants as the initial purpose of recruitment and what is obtained from the results of recruitment. If it does not occur as expected by the organization, the possibility of work activities being less effective and efficient, then the organization is likely to experience failure. According to Achmad (2011:52), by offering a recruitment process that promises a memorable experience, at the end point the company can more freely choose which candidate is the best for the company. Job offers are also not always directly accepted by candidates, therefore, giving an impressive recruitment process experience can increase the chances of candidates accepting job offers given by the company. Data from *talenta.com* shows that 38% of employees who claim to have impressive recruitment experience tend to accept job offers from the company. On the other hand, as many as 62% of candidates who feel they have good recruitment experience will recommend the company to others. For the company's own image, a neatly arranged and impressive recruitment process will add value to the image it has. As many as 87%

of candidates say that an impressive recruitment process can really influence what they think about the company. So it is clear, that the experience of an impressive recruitment process can bring many benefits to the company. Not only questioning the prospective workforce to be netted, the company's HR management is also related to the method or method of recruiting itself. The role of recruiters has shifted, which had relied on face-to-face meetings, has now become more tech-enabled by relying on technology assistance. In terms of effectiveness and efficiency, of course the use of new technology in recruitment will save a lot of time and effort. For example, recruiters do not need to free up time specifically to meet with candidates they have. Without the intention of not respecting existing candidates, but in the name of the effectiveness of the process, simplicity and speed become the main. One use of new technology is interviews using the help of electronic media, specifically through video communication services. Vieple, one of the service providers, said there was rapid growth in the job interview method using the media's assistance. In 2012 Vieple service usage was recorded at 7%. But in 2019 the figure will increase to 52%. This shows that the use of this interview method has begun to be adapted and has become a new recruitment procedure used by many companies.

In the process of adaptation and determining strategic ways for recruitment is not without risk. Experiments carried out will always be accompanied by challenges and risks as well as opportunities. This is why in-depth observations are needed on the method to be used in order to get maximum results. Likewise with the company PT. Toba Pulp Lestari (TPL) is a pulp and paper company in the Lake Toba region, North Sumatra, Indonesia. The giant pulp company is affiliated with the Royal Golden Eagle group and APRIL (Indonesia's second largest pulp and paper company) and is largely owned by Indonesian tycoon, Sukanto Tanoto. For PT. Toba Pulp Lestari,

Tbk Medan located at Jl. Letjend Haryono MT No.A-1, 6th Floor, East Tower, Medan Uniplaza Building, but for the production and plant processes of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari produces around Lake Toba, Porsea and Humbahas. This company we used to hear from the name PT. Inti Indorayon Utama has now changed its name to PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Tbk is a producer of industrial pulp or commonly known as pulp. Its production is sold in the domestic and overseas markets (exports). License capacity of 165 thousand tons/year with a tolerance of 30%. This company's production.

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research used in this research is quantitative research with an associative method to determine the effect or relationship between two or more variables (Sugiyono 2003:11).

This research was conducted at Toba Pulp Lestari domiciled in Uniplaza, East Tower 6th floor Jl. Letjen Haryono Mt No. A-1 Medan, North Sumatra, but if needed for further research at the factory located in Pangombusan Village, Pamaksi District, Toba Samosir Regency from March 2019 to September 2019.

The measurement scale in this study is the Likert scale, which is used to measure the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena (Sugiyono 2012:134). Measurement of variables is done not through questions but through statements and respondents are asked to make choices about the level of agreement in accordance with their perceptions (Sinulingga 2018:162).

According to Sugiyono (2012:117), population is a generalization area that consists of objects/subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study, the study population of 535 people were new employees in Toba Pulp who had just been recruited, had only become employees in

the last 3 years, and had followed the recruitment and training process by PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. To determine the minimum sample required if population size is known, the Slovin formula is used (Umar, 2009:78). From the above data it can be seen that the number of samples used in this study was fulfilled as many as 84 people. The sampling technique used according to Sugiyono (2012:62) is purposive sampling, namely the determination of the sample using certain criteria, namely the number of respondents used as research samples are new employees who were recruited in the last 3 years and attended training by PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea.

Hypothesis testing can be done with the coefficient of determination, simultaneously (F test) and partially (t test). To see the effect of the recruitment process and selection procedure on employee performance simultaneously can be calculated using the simultaneous significance test (F test). This test is conducted to find out how far the influence of an independent variable, namely the recruitment process and selection procedure partially on the variation of the dependent variable, namely employee performance.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)

To see the effect of the recruitment process and selection procedure on employee performance simultaneously can be calculated using simultaneous significance (F test). This test basically shows whether all independent variables included in the regression model have a joint influence on the dependent variable.

F test is used to determine whether the independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on the dependent variable. With the criteria if $F_{count} > F_{table}$ and if the significance level is below 0.05 then the independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on the dependent variable. Based on the results of data processing with the SPSS program, the following results are obtained:

Table 1. F Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	993.239	2	496.619	12.149	.000 ^b
	Residual	3311.178	81	40.879		
	Total	4304.417	83			
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Selection Procedure, Recruitment Process						

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Data Processed)

In Table 1 we can see that the value of Fcount (12,149) > Ftable (3,111). This shows that the independent variable consists of the recruitment process variable (X₁), the selection procedure (X₂), simultaneously positive and significant effect on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y) at PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea.

Partial Significance Test (t Test)

test is carried out to find out how far the influence of an independent variable is the recruitment process and the selection procedure partially on the dependent variable variation, namely employee performance.

The calculated tcount will be obtained and then it will be compared with the ttable value at the level of $\alpha=5\%$ ie obtained by the degree of freedom= $df=n-k$ (n =number of samples and k =total number of variables) $df=84-3=81$, tcount test is a two-way test, then the table used is t 5% or t 0.05 (81)=1.990.

Table 2. t Test

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	24.052	6.441		3.734	.000		
	Recruitment Process	.269	.186	.179	1.446	.152	.617	1.622
	Selection Procedure	.884	.315	.348	2.805	.006	.617	1.622
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance								

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Data Processed)

Thus the partial t test results can be interpreted as follows:

1. Testing recruitment process (X₁) on employee performance (Y) shows a significance of 0.152 > 0.05 while tcount (1.446) < ttable (1.990). Then it can be concluded that the recruitment process variable has a positive and not significant effect on employee performance at PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. Means that although the recruitment process (X₁) variable increased by one unit, the employee performance (Y) of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari will not increase by 0,269 units.

The recruitment process is the process of providing a set of prospective workers/employees who meet the requirements, to be consistent with the company's strategy, insight and values. To help reduce the possibility of leaving

employees who have not worked for a long time, to coordinate recruitment efforts with selection and training programs and to fulfill company responsibilities in efforts to create job opportunities (Siagian, 2009:102).

This is in accordance with the problems faced by PT. Toba Pulp Lestari is the existence of new employees who leave just because there is no wifi facilities in the office, and various reasons for the work environment that is not in accordance with the personality characteristics of employees who have been recruited. PT. Toba pulp Lestari. There is a need for a deeper recruitment process to find out the characteristics of prospective employees who will be recruited not only ready to work in the work environment of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea but able to face the environment far from the city center,

entertainment venues, and external facilities needed by prospective employees who are still in the millennial age category. PT. Toba Pulp also needs to be sensitive to the needs of employees to be able to provide the best performance, so that PT. Toba Pulp Lestari is able to adjust changes in the characteristics of employees who have settled by providing changes in facility policies that have a good impact on employees to improve company performance, and in the recruitment process that needs to be reviewed from personal characteristics screening more personally and objectively so that recruitment strategies are more efficient. And for transparency issues in the results of this study, it is necessary to improve two-way communication between the recruitment committee and prospective employees who follow the recruitment process.

The results of this study are supported by previous research by Rahim (2018) entitled "The Effect of the Recruitment and Selection Process on Employee Performance at PT Indomarco Prismatama Makassar Branch," showing that the Recruitment Process has a positive effect but does not significantly influence employee performance. That makes Selection the most dominant variable affecting the performance of employees at PT Indomarco Prismatama Makassar. Whereas the recruitment process carried out by PT. Toba Pulp Lestari has been good so far but has not had a significant effect on improving employee performance.

2. Testing selection procedure (X_2) on employee performance (Y) shows a significance of $0.006 < 0.05$ while $t_{count} (2.805) > t_{table} (1.990)$. Then it can be concluded that the selection procedure variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the employees of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. Means that if the selection procedure variable (X_2) is increased by one unit then the employee performance (Y) of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari will increase by 0.884 units.

Procedures that must be carried out by the company in making a good selection. Selection procedures according to Simamora (2004:221) are made and adjusted to meet the organizational staffing needs.

The results of this study are supported by previous research by Yullyanti (2009) entitled "Analysis of the Recruitment and Selection Process in Employee Work," that the recruitment carried out properly and accordingly will facilitate the recruitment process to the next stage of the procurement of employees to fill jobs. The most significant recruitment indicator is the selection procedure. The study found that the respondents perceive that good procedures, carried out correctly and aimed at getting reliable employees are an important part that must be carried out. Likewise with the results of this study that the procedures carried out by PT. Toba Pulp Lestari affects the performance of its employees the better the consistency and reality in carrying out the selection procedure, the better it will be to improve the performance of the employees of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea.

So companies need to innovate the system of procedures that have been carried out so far in the selection of the latest employees. Like starting to do online-based selection and reduce manual selection so that the latest employees are also accustomed from the start to face the digital industry 4.0 to get a wider and competent range of applicants.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the research that has been done, it is obtained that the recruitment process and selection procedure simultaneously had a positive and significant effect on employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. The recruitment process partially had a positive but not significant effect on employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. Partial selection procedure had a

positive and significant effect on employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea. Partially the selection procedure is the most dominant variable affecting the employee performance of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari Porsea.

Suggestion

As suggestions that can be implemented based on the results of the study are:

1. For PT. Toba Pulp Lestari, based on the conclusion that variable selection procedure effect employee performance positively and significantly, things that need to be corrected to overcome weaknesses that are found to be inconsistent during the selection process, that each applicant follows the selection in different times, so it is necessary to innovate the selection procedure system that has been done so far by starting to do online-based selection and reduce manual selection to get consistency in the selection procedure. This innovation is effective in getting more and more qualified applicants, this will also make new employees familiar with the digital system to deal with the digital industry 4.0.

2. For PT. Toba Pulp Lestari, based on the conclusion that the recruitment process variable influences employee performance positively but is not significant, but weaknesses are found so that there is an opportunity to improve the recruitment process that occurs when new employees leave due to the lack of wifi facilities for employees and various work environment reasons that do not match the personality characteristics of employees so things that need to be fixed. Things that can be improved in the recruitment process need to do a deeper screening test screening and determine objectivity standards in order to find the personality of employees who meet the qualifications according to the characteristics of the work environment of PT. Toba Pulp Lestari.

3. For researchers, it is hoped that they can continue to deepen and apply human

resource theory in particular to recruitment by adding variables that have not been examined in this research such as training, workload, work environment, work placement. And is expected to research on a larger scale.

4. For other companies, this research is expected to be able to provide information and input for other companies that will develop recruitment strategies to improve employee performance.

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